

Capitalization and Co-operative Competitiveness in Nigeria: The Linkage

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ABSTRACT

In the contemporary world, co-operatives are challenged by very competitive global market economy. Co-operatives have the tendency of breaking imperfect markets; however, its dual nature creates limited sources of capital which seems to affect the competitiveness of cooperatives. This qualitative paper examined various literatures with the objective of evaluating co-operative as a competitive yardstick and also to determine the linkage between capitalization and co-operative competitiveness. The findings made include that an increased co-operative capitalization makes co-operative to be more competitive and the existence of a co-operative in a market will force profit-maximizing firms to behave more competitively. Those co-operatives which are viable and competitive in the present are those that generate other innovative sources of funding while maintaining their co-operative identity. Based on the findings, it was recommended that for co-operative to become and remain competitive in Nigeria and by extension global economic market, they must be able to source for capital from the non-traditional sources without losing their identity.

Key words: Capitalization, Competitiveness, Co-operatives, Linkage

INTRODUCTION

The global economy has become very competitive, various firms and establishments try to improve their capital base, become innovative by creating newer products and improving their efficiency to remain relevant in the competitive global economy. A co-operative is like the Investor Owned Firm (IOF), the property of the investor, but these investors are also members of the co-operative, which means that they are the users and managers of the firm, (Milford, 2004). The way co-operatives interact with investor owned firms (IOFs) in the market is an important aspect of their function, particularly in the market situations characterized by imperfect competition. Very often co-operatives are formed as a response to market failure. Azevedo and Gitaby (2010) pinpointed that it is possible to join high technology, competitiveness, technological innovation to the co-operative movement and

self-management. Currently, there are a number of changes in global economic conditions that confront and challenge the viability of co-operatives in the developed world, including the decreasing flow of development assistance, globalization of trade and deregulation of domestic markets, industrialization and vertical integration of agricultural product and food systems among others. Today information is increasingly available cheaply and rapidly, transport is faster and competition more intense. These changes challenge traditional mechanisms of solidarity and require the adoption of new capitalization strategies and general efficiency to conform to the prevailing competitive market.

The objectives of this study therefore were to examine the linkage between capitalization and co-operative competitiveness and to x-ray co-operatives as competitive yardstick in Nigeria.

This paper is divided into three sections. The first section covers the introduction, the second deals with conceptual issues, co-operative as a competitive yardstick as well as capitalization and co-operative competitiveness while the last section covers the conclusion and recommendations.

CONCEPTUAL ISSUES

Competitiveness

Competitiveness pertains to the ability and performance of a firm, sub-sector or country to sell and supply goods and services in a given market, in relation to the ability and performance of other firms, sub sectors or countries in the same market (Wikipedia, 2012). The concept of competitiveness has emerged as a new paradigm in economic development. Competitiveness captures the awareness of both the limitations and challenges posed by global competition, at a time when effective government action is constrained by budgetary constraints and the private sector faces significant barriers to competing in domestic and international market.

Capitalization

Capitalization refers to the amounts and types of long-term financing used by a firm which may include common stock, preferred stock, retained, earning and long term debt. A firm with capitalization including little or no long term debt is considered to be financed very conservatively. Green (2012) described capitalization as a measure of a company's total value. It is not the only measure, but one that financial investors use to appraise and value a company.

Concepts of Member-User and Member-Investor

Members of co-operatives perform two roles; as users/suppliers and as investors. In IOFs, the users are different from the investors. The users are the customers who want to have very good quality products at the least possible price while the investors are the shareholders who want to have very large return on investment. In co-operative the users (customers) are the same as the investors (shareholders). They are all members of the co-operative.

To be successful, a co-operative must price its goods and services in a way that both attracts members' usage and generates capital-either through retention of surplus or increased member investment. With increased market competition, members will tend to seek providers who serve them best (co-operative or the IOF).

The Financial Structure of Co-operatives

A co-operative does not distribute the generated surplus according to capital holdings. The patronage dividend is usual distributed according to level of members' patronage, which means that the more members patronize the co-operative, the more they gain. A co-operative strives to maximize returns to members rather than to maximize profit. There is a uniform membership fee which implies that all members have equal share, and the votes are usually distributed according to the one-man, one-vote principle. Member capital is actually the lifeblood of true co-operatives even though it could be necessary to seek for external funding.

Co-operatives have three main sources of Finance.

- The most important source is equity capital (members as users and investor). Without this base, it is difficult to attract funds from others.
- The second source is retained surpluses, especial "unallocated" funds that are not assigned for distribution to members. These are known as institutional capital, which belongs to the co-operative and can be liquidated only if the co-operative incurs losses or dissolves.

- Finally, external funding can also be readily obtained from commercial sources (though usually at a higher cost) in a number of forms that include loans, equipment financing and so on.

The core problem of capital formation in co-operatives is in the inherent conflict between.

- Members' interests as users or suppliers and
- Members' interest as investors.

Ananiadis, Notta, and Oustapassidis (2003), contended that one of the most complicated issues, which concern the financial management of both co-operatives and the IOFs, is the relation between the capital structure of a firm and its ability to compete with investor owned firms (IOFs) operating within the same market. The financial structure of the co-operative is impacted by the management system, fundamentally differing from that of IOFs with the ensuing consequences as regards the dividends and interest policies. However, it is vital for co-operatives to achieve the optimum capital structure in order to be in a position to fund both the necessary investors and strategies which will render them competitive (Oustapassidis and Notta,1997). Otherwise they will not be able to survive in the long run within markets where both competitive strategies and investment in new technology are applied by the existing firms.

Equities of co-operatives are supplied by members by obtaining equity financing internally, co-operative do not incur the cost of soliciting investment capital in the capital market (Ling 2012). Generally, the more the member use and benefit from the co-operative's services, the more surplus funds the co-operative will generate, and the more members, will be encourage to invest additional funds to maintain or increase those benefits. The traditional forms of member capitalization include; membership and service institutional capital, accounts payable to members and member deposit.

Methodology

The paper is a descriptive and qualitative study. Thus, it fundamentally based on scholarly library research enriched with online sources, institutions' and government's publications. Relying majorly on

secondary sources of data collection, the paper uses the combination of documentary, analytical and descriptive method to consider the various contexts of Cooperative Capitalization and it affects competitiveness of Cooperatives in Nigeria and in x-raying Cooperative as a competitive yardstick.

Table 1 therefore analyzes the sources of member capital, their advantages and disadvantages to some stakeholders.

Sources of Member Capital, Advantages and Disadvantages

Table 1: Sources of Member Capital, their Advantages and Disadvantages to the Member-User, Member-investor and Cooperative Manager

Type of Capital	The member-user	The members-investor	The management
<p>Shares:</p> <p>Membership in a coop requires the purchase of one or more shares</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>Right to do business, participate in general meetings, stand for office, often with only a small commitment of funds.</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>Shares from patronage may be disproportionate to current patronage of oldest and newest members, creating a Frees Rider Problem (i.e. when patronage of new members does not make the coop more efficient and competitive by producing significant economies of scale).</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>Long-term savings vehicle where few savings alternatives may be available: interest may be paid; supports the coop.</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>Limited return, loses value with inflation, may be difficult to redeem. Value may not fully reflect good performance by the coop.</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>Basic source of finance; usually low cost; board may control share redemption.</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>Dividend expectation may be difficult to fulfill in bad years; share base may be unstable if active members withdraw or old members retire or die and their heirs do not assume ownership of the shares.</p>
<p>Institutional Capital</p> <p>By retaining surpluses,</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>lower costs which may increase payouts</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>lowercosts which may permit higher interest</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>Almost costless, redeemable only through losses or in liquidation “strongest” form of</p>

instead of allocating to members	<p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>funds might otherwise have been paid to members</p>	on shares	<p>coop capital possible windfall gains</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>incentives for making losses</p>
<p>Deposits:</p> <p>Funds members leave with the coop when they do not withdraw in full payments received for patronage</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>Supports the coop; savings may be linked to payouts automatically</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>Could have been paid to members as patronage rebate.</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>convenience, interest-earning, supports the coop</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>minimum balance may be required: lack of risk diversification – their safety is tied to coop performance.</p>	<p>Advantages: source of funds, often seasonal</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>may be difficult to manage, may require more office space, security, staff and longer hours of business, not reliable for long term purposes and may expose the society to excess liability.</p>
<p>Accounts payable:</p> <p>owed to members for patronage, but not yet paid to them</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>dependable near-term source of income</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>funds are not immediately available</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>dependable near-term source of income</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>funds are not immediately available</p>	<p>Advantages:</p> <p>costless source of funds that may give management flexibility in fixing payout dates</p> <p>Disadvantages:</p> <p>requires more management than immediate payouts</p>

Source: Adapted from Chaddad and Cook (2003)

Most strategies for co-operative business development require increased capital. Therefore such strategies should focus not only on improving operational efficiency and increasing member patronage but also on attracting more member capital and new members.

CO-OPERATIVE AS A COMPETITIVE YARDSTICK

Ling (2012) stated that the presence of co-operative challenges other market participant to operate efficiently and thus strengthens the competitive market mechanism. Edelman and Dunn (2009) explained that direct alignment with the interest and needs of its customers affects not only the way the co-operative operates as a business, but can also have impact on the conduct and performance of non co-operative firms in the market place. Co-operative presence in a market place can help to ensure that consumer needs are met with a more competitive market place. This theory of the co-operative firm is known within the academic community as the “competitive Yardstick”. The co-operatives offerings present a standard or yardstick by which all firms’ offerings can be compared.

Hoffman and Royer (1997) argued that the logic behind the yardstick is that the co-operative will offer more favourable prices because of its unique structure. Competing firms must match the co-operatives performance to avoid losing patrons to it. Consequently, the market will move towards competitive equilibrium.

Edelman and Dunn (2009) averred that the impact of co-operatives on the performance of a market place does not grow out of the characteristics of the given market, rather from the characteristics of the co-operative form of business, its participation in the market, and its focus on the needs of the member consumers. Thus, the best evidence of the competitive yardstick effect of co-operatives is seen in other industries and sectors where co-operatives have developed a more significant presence.

Ling (2012) summarized the market performance of farmers co-operative in market competitiveness thus;

- Co-operatives make it feasible for farmers who otherwise may not have outlets for their products to join together and have market access.
- *Co-operative* can be of any size and are organized for carrying out specific business functions for member-producers

- Co-operatives afford farmers the organizational sizes that are necessary for exercising countervailing power to effectively deal with other market participants.
- Co-operatives are pro-market; they let the market supply and demand price be the guidance for producers.
- Co-operatives are means for farmers to promote and maintain competition – as the competitive yardstick.

Capitalization and Co-operatives' Competitiveness

Quite unlike public companies, co-operatives do not issue its shares to the general public for subscription or sale; this means that their capital base is usually smaller compared to other market operators who exist in the same competitive environment. Co-operatives that successfully compete with IOFs can increase their price cost margin and thus, their profitability and their ability to invest in both sales promotion strategies and modern technology.

Ananiadis et al (2003) asserted that the higher the proportion of undistributed profits to total co-operative profit, the cheaper the cost of capital used to finance investment required for development and co-operative competitiveness. This, they argued, may not satisfy short run interests of the co-operative members who may prefer the distribution of all or a great proportion of co-operative surplus as dividends among them. If co-operative management applies a policy satisfying short term interests of the membership, then it will find it difficult to finance development programmes by borrowing capital from financial institutions, which requires the payment of an extra cost for the interest.

Increased member patronage provides an important source of member capital. Larger member-users are necessary to contribute more investment capital than members providing little patronage. Most co-operatives in developing countries have to rely on member generated funds to finance their operations. The benefits of heavier reliance on member funds as the primary source of capital far outweigh the costs.

In a study by Ananiadis et al (2003), it was found that the degree to which equity capital covers fixed assets, the degree of self-finance, the capital to sale ratio along with the market share are positively

associated with profitability of both co-operatives and IOFs. Improving efficiency is also important for the mobilization of funds because it enables a co-operative to offer competitive prices and to pay promptly, thus securing and keeping members’ loyalty.

Effect of Capitalization on Competitiveness

Table: Competitive Effect of Traditional and Innovative Capitalization

<i>Traditionals Capitals</i>	<i>Innovative Capitals</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Membership shares</i> ▪ <i>Membership and service fees</i> ▪ <i>Retention of surplus and institutional Capital</i> ▪ <i>Account Payable to members</i> ▪ <i>Member Deposit</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Deferred Payment revolving funds (patronage rebate credited to members’ account payable</i> ▪ <i>Strategic Equity Alliance (Joint venture with other firms</i> ▪ <i>Grants and loans (Other external Capital)</i>
Effect on Co-operatives’ Competitiveness	Effect on Co-operatives’ Competitiveness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Stimulate growth and productivity ➤ Increase member surplus, hence motivating members to become more innovative in their products ➤ Yield large capital to finance internal growth ➤ Strong traditional capitals increase the chance of obtaining fund from outside which help the co-operative to compete favourably in the market ➤ Low cost of servicing ➤ Could create financial self-reliance ➤ Low risk capital formation and sustainability of fund 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Create opportunity for more economic operations and flexibility in business strategies ➤ Generation of Intellectual ideas from outside lenders ➤ Improved economies of scale ➤ Help to keep pace with increasing competitive market ➤ Interaction with outside suppliers and allies ➤ keep the co-operative updated in the market ➤ Strategic equity alliance creates a synergy impact

Source: Compiled by the Authors

The greater the amount of capital held by the co-operative the greater its ability to purchase more efficient technology invest in staff training and education, and make other improvement in its business. Also, the higher the institutional and member capital, the more outside lenders such as banks and suppliers will be willing to lend to the co-operative hence making it to stimulate the desired competition. Co-operative capital formation is essential for survival in a competitive and risky world. Successful co-operatives innovate in the development of their businesses and in their capitalization strategies and methods.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Co-operatives with sufficient funds are able to invest in training and technology to reduce costs and to increase or improve production. The higher the co-operative capitalization, the higher its competitive ability. Internal capital is used by most co-operatives to facilitate their activities. It is imperative that co-operatives adapt to the global competitive economic market by findings new ways to finance their operations and compete, while maintaining their co-operative identity. The greater majority of modern co-operatives that succeed in addressing competitive situations choose to adapt and innovate, moving away from a strict interpretation of traditional co-operative principles towards definition of a more modern co-operative identity which recognizes that equal importance of the member both as user and as investor. Internal funding may be insufficient or not available when it would be most useful hence co-operatives should engage on improved capitalization through outside capital.

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